

Fetal Death Associated with Pathological Hypercoiling and Torsion of the Umbilical Cord: A Case Report

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ABSTRACT

Hypercoiling of the umbilical cord is a rare cause of intrauterine fetal death. Most reported cases include thrombosis or inflammation, making vascular obliteration without these findings unusual and clinically relevant. Objective: To present a case of intrauterine fetal death due to hypercoiling and torsion of the umbilical cord, highlighting uncommon clinical and histopathological findings. Case report: A 28-year-old woman with chronic hypertension and overweight, with irregular prenatal care, presented with absence of fetal movements accompanied by anxiety and insomnia. Ultrasound confirmed fetal demise at 27 weeks with oligohydramnios. Labor was induced with misoprostol, resulting in a female fetus weighing 990 grams, with abdominal necrosis and ecchymosis. The umbilical cord measured 66 cm, showed 39 twists, torsion, and constriction at the fetal insertion. Histopathological examination revealed obliteration of two arteries and one vein without thrombosis or inflammation. The patient had a favorable postpartum course without maternal complications and received psychological support and reproductive counseling. Conclusions: This case confirms that severe hypercoiling with torsion can cause intrauterine fetal death even in the absence of thrombosis. It underscores the need for systematic placental and umbilical cord examination in cases of fetal demise, reinforcement of timely prenatal care, and comprehensive support for affected patients.

KEYWORDS: Umbilical cord hypercoiling; umbilical torsion; intrauterine fetal death; fetal vascular malperfusion; Wharton’s jelly; umbilical coiling index.

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INTRODUCTION

The umbilical cord is an essential structure for fetal survival, serving as the anatomical and physiological connection between the placenta and the fetus. Its helical coiling is considered an evolutionary adaptation that provides flexibility and resistance to compression and traction, thereby ensuring adequate fetoplacental blood flow. Helicity is typically established by the ninth week of gestation and remains relatively constant throughout pregnancy.¹

To quantitatively assess the degree of coiling, Edmonds introduced the concept of the “torsion index” in 1954, which was later simplified by Strong et al. into the Umbilical

Coiling Index (UCI). This index is defined as the ratio between the number of twists and the cord length. Normally coiled cords have approximately one twist every 5 cm. A hypocoiled cord is defined as having one twist per 10 cm of cord segment, whereas a hypercoiled cord presents more than three twists per 10 cm.

Both extremes are associated with obstetric and perinatal complications.²

Clinically, hypocoiling has been associated with preterm birth, oligohydramnios, and intrauterine fetal demise, whereas hypercoiling is linked to intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR), low birth weight, and fetal heart rate

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abnormalities during labor.² Moreover, hypercoiling has been reported as a recurrent finding in fetal demise cases, representing up to one-quarter of intrauterine fetal deaths in some series.⁴

The blood vessels of a hypercoiled cord are more prone to kinking, compression, and torsion, which may acutely compromise fetal blood flow and lead to hypoxia, acidosis, and adverse perinatal outcomes.⁴ Histopathological findings often described include fetal vessel thrombosis, avascular villi, villous stromal karyorrhexis, and normoblastemia, all consistent with fetal vascular malperfusion (FVM).³ In severe cases, cord torsion may result in complete obliteration of the vascular lumen, precipitating sudden fetal death, typically in the second trimester when the cord length increases and fetal activity becomes more vigorous.³

Despite advances in Doppler ultrasound and sonographic assessment of the UCI, antenatal detection of abnormal coiling remains limited. Significant discrepancies exist between prenatal and postnatal measurements, and the predictive value is insufficient to support routine clinical use.¹ Therefore, antenatal identification of pathological hypercoiling continues to pose a diagnostic challenge.

Fetal death associated with pathological umbilical cord hypercoiling and torsion is rare, with a multifactorial etiology and poorly defined risk factors. Excessive cord length, decreased Wharton's jelly, and increased fetal movements have been proposed as potential mechanisms.⁵ However, the absence of reliable predictors and the low sensitivity of current diagnostic methods limit prevention strategies.

In this context, case reports are valuable tools to broaden understanding of this condition, describe clinical and histopathological findings, and generate hypotheses that may guide future research. This article aims to report a case of fetal death associated with pathological hypercoiling and torsion of the umbilical cord, emphasizing the importance of recognizing this entity as a potential cause of intrauterine fetal demise.

CASE REPORT

We present the case of a 28-year-old mestizo Mexican woman, employed as an administrative worker, gravida 3 para 1 abortus 1. Her previous delivery was at term, vaginal, without complications, with a healthy newborn. The prior miscarriage was spontaneous and medically managed; no histopathological studies or karyotype were performed. Medical history included well-controlled chronic arterial hypertension and overweight (pre-pregnancy BMI 29), treated with alpha-methyldopa 500 mg every 8 hours during pregnancy. Her lifestyle was characterized by a diet high in carbohydrates and fats, low in vegetables, and minimal physical activity. She denied tobacco, alcohol, or illicit drug use. She had a stable partner and family support. No history of diagnosed depression or anxiety was reported, although she referred to previous episodes of work-related stress. There was no family history of thrombophilia, fetal death,

preeclampsia, or cardiovascular disease. Genetic testing revealed normal maternal and paternal karyotypes.

Prenatal care was irregular, with only two consultations. First-trimester screening was normal. The patient cited financial and work-related difficulties as reasons for poor adherence to prenatal care, limiting timely diagnosis. No prior ultrasounds assessing the umbilical cord or Doppler studies were performed.

She presented to the emergency department due to absence of fetal movements for one day, accompanied by anxiety, insomnia, and decreased appetite, without abdominal pain, vaginal bleeding, or fluid loss. Vital signs were: blood pressure 120/70 mmHg, maternal heart rate 80 bpm, afebrile. Abdominal examination revealed a soft, non-tender uterus with fundal height of 26 cm, no uterine tone increase or activity, and no fetal heart tones detected by Doppler. Pelvic examination showed a posterior, long, closed, and soft cervix, without transvaginal discharge.

Obstetric ultrasound revealed a 27-week fetus by biparietal diameter and femur length, cephalic presentation, estimated fetal weight of 990 g, decreased amniotic fluid (oligohydramnios), and anterior fundal placenta grade 0. No fetal cardiac activity was detected by color Doppler. A diagnosis of intrauterine fetal demise was established. Differential diagnoses included placental insufficiency, placental abruption, fetoplacental thrombosis, congenital infections, and chromosomal anomalies; however, these were excluded based on negative serological tests and normal parental karyotypes.

Labor induction was performed with vaginal misoprostol 200 µg every 4 hours, up to a total dose of 800 µg, with good tolerance and no need for additional medications. A single female fetus of 27 weeks (990 g) was delivered vaginally, with Apgar scores 0/0. The fetus showed maceration, no major external malformations, but necrosis and edema of the abdominal region, periumbilical ecchymosis, and violaceous macerated skin in the same area. The placenta was complete, measured 18 cm in diameter and 2 cm thick, with normal gross weight and appearance. The umbilical cord displayed paracentral insertion, length of 66 cm, thickness of 1.5 cm, and 39 twists, resulting in a coiling index of 0.82 coils/cm, consistent with hypercoiling. Marked torsion was noted at the fetal-umbilical junction, with a pronounced constriction at the site of insertion. No true or false knots were identified.

Histopathological evaluation of the umbilical cord at its mid-portion revealed two arteries and one vein with preserved lumens, without fibrosis or inflammation. At the fetal-umbilical junction, complete luminal obliteration of both arteries and the vein was observed, without thrombosis or inflammation. These findings confirmed umbilical blood flow occlusion secondary to cord torsion in the setting of hypercoiling.

Maternal serologic studies (TORCH, syphilis, HIV, hepatitis B/C, antiphospholipid antibodies, lupus anticoagulant) were

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negative. Thrombophilia screening was negative, and both parental karyotypes were normal.

The patient remained hemodynamically stable without hemorrhagic or infectious complications in the immediate postpartum period and was discharged 48 hours later. She received psychological support after the loss, followed by preconception counseling and family planning education. At the four-week follow-up, she demonstrated adequate physical

and emotional recovery, with good adherence to care. No adverse events or unexpected complications were reported.

Based on clinical, ultrasound, and histopathological findings, the cause of intrauterine fetal demise was determined to be umbilical blood flow occlusion due to cord torsion and stenosis associated with pathological hypercoiling. Written informed consent for publication was obtained from the family, and photographic documentation of the umbilical cord and fetus was secured.

Figure 1. Macroscopic evidence of intrauterine fetal demise. Umbilical cord with torsion and pathological hypercoiling; fetal abdomen with marked distension, generalized ecchymosis, and postmortem skin changes.

DISCUSSION

Umbilical cord hypercoiling (UCI > 0.30 coils/cm) has been established in the literature as a relevant finding in the pathogenesis of intrauterine fetal demise. Multiple studies have demonstrated that complete placental and umbilical cord examination, including determination of the coiling index, can significantly reduce the number of stillbirths classified as unexplained.^{4,7} In this case, despite maternal risk factors such as chronic hypertension and overweight, serologic, immunologic, and genetic evaluations were negative, allowing the fetal death to be directly attributed to the umbilical cord abnormality documented both macroscopically and histologically.

In a retrospective analysis of 77 cases of intrauterine fetal demise, Dutman et al. reported an 18% incidence of hypercoiling, with a significant negative correlation between umbilical cord hypercoiling and gestational age at fetal death. The most severe cases tended to occur earlier in gestation and showed a stronger association with fetal thrombosis and cord

stenosis.⁷ Our findings are consistent with this pattern: fetal demise occurred at 27 weeks, with a high UCI (0.82 coils/cm) and marked torsion, reinforcing the hypothesis that severe hypercoiling commonly manifests in mid- to early-gestational periods and is associated with fatal outcomes.

Ernst et al. (2013) described specific macroscopic cord coiling patterns—wavy, rope-like, segmented, and interlaced—and found that segmented and interlaced patterns, characterized by deeper indentations in cord diameter, were significantly associated with chronic fetal vascular obstruction and stillbirth compared with wavy or rope-like patterns. Additionally, right-sided torsion was associated with increased risk of fetal vascular compromise, emphasizing the need to consider not only the coil density but also the morphology of cord coiling.⁸

Regarding antenatal evaluation, Singireddy et al. (2023) examined ultrasound-measured UCI in 150 second-trimester pregnancies. Although correlations were found with maternal comorbidities such as gestational hypertension and anemia,

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abnormal UCI did not consistently predict adverse perinatal outcomes, limiting routine clinical utility.⁹ Larger-scale studies are needed to refine diagnostic thresholds and determine predictive value. In our case, the patient had normal first-trimester screening and no subsequent Doppler studies, highlighting the current limitations of ultrasound in anticipating adverse outcomes in hypercoiling and the need for targeted diagnostic tools.

More recently, Clement (2025) analyzed 389 fetal autopsies and reported 75 cases of hypercoiling with stenosis (HCS), confirming it as one of the most common etiologies of stillbirth. Advanced maternal age (≥ 35 years), multiparity, longer cords, and elevated UCI were associated with HCS. A key finding was the role of insufficient or poorly developed Wharton's jelly at the fetal-umbilical junction as a central factor in vascular obstruction and fetal demise.¹¹ In our case, vascular obliteration without thrombosis or inflammation may reflect this mechanism.

Overall, umbilical cord hypercoiling should not be regarded as an isolated finding but part of a spectrum of cord abnormalities—including torsion, stenosis, and Wharton's jelly deficiency—that can compromise fetoplacental circulation. Detailed examination of the placenta and cord in stillbirth cases should be standard practice, as it provides essential diagnostic information and reduces the frequency of unexplained fetal deaths.

Strengths of this report include diagnosis via ultrasound, corroborating macroscopic and histopathological findings, and comprehensive maternal evaluation ruling out infectious, immunologic, and genetic etiologies. The main limitation was insufficient prenatal surveillance, including lack of serial ultrasound and Doppler evaluation, which prevented early detection. This case underscores diagnostic challenges in patients facing socioeconomic barriers, where limited prenatal care may delay recognition of fetal compromise.

Key lessons include the importance of systematic umbilical cord assessment in stillbirth evaluation, timely prenatal monitoring, and use of standardized protocols to reduce unexplained fetal losses. From the patient's perspective, the mother reported initial sadness and anxiety but expressed feeling supported by the medical team, valuing the psychological assistance and preconception counseling provided for future pregnancies.

CONCLUSION

This case demonstrates that umbilical cord hypercoiling with torsion and stenosis at the fetal-umbilical junction is a clear cause of intrauterine fetal demise, even in the absence of significant maternal pathology. Detailed placental and cord evaluation should be considered essential in stillbirth diagnostic protocols, as it clarifies underlying causes previously labeled as unexplained and informs reproductive counseling. Current evidence suggests that integrating advanced ultrasound techniques, including 2D/3D imaging and Doppler, may improve prenatal assessment, although

larger population studies are needed to establish reliable diagnostic thresholds. Our report underscores the importance of early recognition and rigorous documentation of umbilical cord abnormalities to aid prevention, optimize obstetric management, and reduce fetal complications.

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CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

None declared.

ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

The patient was fully informed about the diagnosis, procedures, and potential risks. Written informed consent was obtained for medical management and publication of this case report, in accordance with the ethical principles of the Declaration of Helsinki and institutional protocols.

REFERENCES

- I. Slack, J. C., Boyd, T. K., & Carreon, C. K. (2022). *Recurrent Second Trimester Fetal Demise Caused by Hypercoiled Umbilical Cords*. *Fetal and Pediatric Pathology*, 42(3), 492–497. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15513815.2022.2142490>
- II. Tuania, A., Cecchi, A., Carboni, E., Resta, S., Bonasoni, M. P., & Ruano, R. (2023). *Umbilical cord abnormalities and pregnancy outcome: A narrative review*. *Healthcare*, 11(19), 2634. <https://doi.org/10.3390/healthcare11192634>
- III. Moyano, G., García, R., Barrera, C., & Corsi, O. (2022). *Hiperenrollamiento con torsión del cordón umbilical como causa de muerte fetal: reporte de caso*. *Revista Chilena de Obstetricia y Ginecología*, 87(2), 158–165. <https://doi.org/10.4067/S0717-75262022000200158>
- IV. Nakamura, M., Hasegawa, J., Takita, H., & Sekizawa, A. (2021). *Amnioinfusion and bed rest may effectively improve the insufficient circulation of the umbilical cord in pregnant women with hypercoiled cord and oligohydramnios*. *Journal of Medical Cases*, 12(1), 1–4. <https://doi.org/10.14740/jmc3581>
- V. Akgün, N., Köflüfl, N., Köflüfl, A., & Yardımcı, F. (2016). *Umbilical cord stenosis and umbilical cord torsion: A case report*. *Perinatal Journal*, 24(1), 47–50. <https://doi.org/10.2399/prn.16.0241009>
- VI. Valera Rodríguez, N., Castro, C. S., Martínez Navarro, J., Fumero Roldán, L., & Rodríguez León,

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- J. E. (2024). Alteraciones de la placenta y sus anejos en muestras procedentes de muertes fetales. *Medisur*, 22(1). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10649334>
- VII. Dutman, A. E., Nikkels, P. G. J., Koek, G. H., van de Vosse, E., & Oepkes, D. (2015). Umbilical hypercoiling in second- and third-trimester intrauterine fetal death. *Pediatric and Developmental Pathology*, 18(2), 81–87. <https://doi.org/10.2350/14-07-1527-OA.1>
- VIII. Ernst, L. M., Minturn, L., Huang, M. H., Curry, E., Su, E. J., & Miller, E. S. (2013). Gross patterns of umbilical cord coiling: Correlations with placental histology and stillbirth. *Placenta*, 34(7), 583–589. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.placenta.2013.04.011>
- IX. Singireddy, A., Patnaik, S., Bera, R., & Dash, S. S. (2023). Antenatal evaluation of umbilical coiling index and its correlation with perinatal outcome. *Journal of Clinical and Diagnostic Research*, 17(12), QC01–QC05. <https://doi.org/10.7860/JCDR/2023/62554.1838>
- X. Slack, J. C., Boyd, T. K., & Carreon, C. K. (2023). Recurrent second trimester fetal demise caused by hypercoiled umbilical cords. *Fetal and Pediatric Pathology*, 42(3), 492–497. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15513815.2022.2142490>
- XI. Clement, A., Mendoza, A., Wixom, C., & Zhang, P. (2025). Umbilical cord hypercoiling with stricture and intrauterine fetal death: Association with maternal factors and implications for pathogenesis. *Fetal and Pediatric Pathology*, Advance online publication. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15513815.2025.2507250>